

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

DIFFERENTIAL TEACHING METHOD IN LANGUAGE LERANING

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Abstract

Schools are attended by children with common features typical of a social group and individual characteristics. Students differ from each other in terms of the characteristics of mental activity, physical development, interests, etc. The teacher organizes training from the first grade for the average level. It is necessary to build teaching on the method of differential approach. Depending on their individual characteristics and level of preparation, students will study the program materials at different depths, and all children will be involved in the learning process during the lesson. Students with various limitations delay, intellectual passivity have a special need for differential education. Due to their low learning activity and skills, an untimely and incorrectly selected teaching method can include them in the category of "chronic" retarded children. These children develop intellectually during games and practical activities.

Keywords: common features, social groups, individual characteristics, differential approach

Introduction

During teaching, it is important that all students work enthusiastically, enjoy language learning, consciously and deeply absorb the program material. Secondary schools are attended by children with both common features typical of a social group and individual, special developmental characteristics. Students studying in these schools differ from each other in terms of the characteristics of mental activity, physical development, skills, interests, etc [3].

The teacher organizes training from the first grade for the average level, that is, for students with average development, average level of preparation, average learning abilities [17]. This leads to the fact that the development of gifted children is artificially stopped, they lose interest in the learning process that does not require mental stress. Learning can be online [4] and offline [5]. "Weak" students, on the contrary, fall into chronic backwardness, and also lose interest in training that requires excessive mental stress from them. At this time, certain questions arise:

1. How to ensure quality education for everyone within 45 minutes? That is, how to build the learning process in accordance with the level of both "weak" and "strong" children?
2. How to use time?
3. How to increase students' interest in learning?
4. How to accustom students to independent work?

It is necessary to build teaching on the method of a differential approach. In this case, depending on their individual characteristics and level of preparation, students will study the program materials at different depths, and all children will be involved in the learning process during the lesson. "Differentiation" (difference) in Latin means "division", that is, the separation of the whole into different parts, forms, levels [8].

This is a complex of methodological, psychopedagogical and organizational measures that ensure the comprehensive education of different groups of students [18]. The purpose of differentiation is to

ensure that everyone continues to learn at the level of their abilities and capabilities. Students with various limitations, mental problems, mental development delay, intellectual passivity have a special need for differential education. Thus, due to their low learning activity and skills, an untimely and incorrectly selected teaching method can include them in the category of "chronic" retarded children. These children develop intellectually during games and practical activities [13]. They are characterized by an attempt to avoid active mental activity [2].

When building the training process, it is necessary to take into account their mental characteristics - slow formation of knowledge, intellectual passivity, fatigue during mental activity. The optimal method for these children in the early stages is to use tasks that are relatively slow, with more visuality and specific instructions, the solution method of which can be shown by the student, allow for more independent work, and gradually increase the level of difficulty [16].

It is important to focus on motivation that develops learning interests. A characteristic feature of working with these students is to dispel the ideas of "incompetence" and "deficiency" that they have formed about themselves, based on the principle of active influence. Studies based on international experience show that the factors that eliminate persistent lag are the student's belief in his or her own strength, learning abilities and capabilities. It is necessary to convince (make realistic) students with disabilities or limitations that they can understand and learn the educational material: "It is difficult, but it does not mean that it is impossible".

Main body

A differentiated approach is not to allocate attention only to "weak" students, but also to students with high mental development, inclinations and abilities to various types of activities, and a high interest in learning. Conditions should be created in the school that ensure the comprehensive development of the abilities of all children. At students who are deeply interested in certain areas, with abilities and

inclinations should be identified. An approach that does not equalize all students, but that corresponds to the individual characteristics of each and ensures their comprehensive development is needed.

The difference is also manifested in the types of intelligence: some students have logical-mathematical intelligence, others verbal-linguistic, and others bodily-kinesthetic intelligence (you can find more information about this in Howard Gardner's book "Multiple Intelligence"). The educational process should be aimed at the development of each of them. That is why during teaching, especially when presenting new material, a wide place should be given to the use of visual aids. For example, schemes, drawings, posters, cards reflecting the topic, etc. Taking into account the individual characteristics of students' thinking, special requirements are made for the explanation of educational material [1].

It should be not only informative and accessible, but also emotional, colorful, creating certain imagination and visual images in the student. It is necessary to create optimal conditions for the development of the personality, taking into account the individual characteristics of the child.

Positive aspects of differential education:

1. "Strong" students have the opportunity to devote time;
2. "Weak" students can be given attention and monitored;
3. The self-esteem of the "weak" student increases
4. The motivation level of the "strong" students increases.

Disadvantages of differential learning: - "Weak" students cannot keep up with the "strong" ones: the motivation level in the "weak" groups decreases. Two types of differentiation are noted:

1. External differentiation - This involves the creation of special schools, classes and intra-school cognitive and artistic circles.
2. Internal differentiation - This involves the organization of intra-class work.

Stages of intra-class differentiation:

1. Determining criteria for creating groups.
2. Conducting diagnostics based on selected criteria (more accurate information is provided by testing at different levels).
3. Dividing students into groups based on diagnostics.
4. Determining differentiation methods, preparing differential tasks.
5. Implementing a differential approach at certain stages of the lesson.
6. Diagnostic control of the results. Based on this, the composition of the groups and the nature of differential tasks may change.

How to organize the lesson in this case? - Example: The class can be divided into 3 groups and individual work can be carried out with each group (the number and composition of group members may vary). During the lesson, work is carried out in small groups of 6-8 people. Each group works with the teacher for 7-10 minutes in the lesson. This is the optimal time for effective and intensive work [12]. Thus, each group can

work with the teacher for 45 minutes, that is, the teacher pays attention to each child [2].

The advantage of this method is that the teacher can evenly distribute his attention among the children. While the teacher is working with the next group, other groups independently perform the task. Differentiation does not create additional difficulties and allows you to change the nature of the transfer of new material, learning, the number of tasks, the pace of work, etc. This method takes into account the functional state of each child, their working ability, fatigue, and, if necessary, creates conditions for rest, change of situation, effective sports minutes, and reduction of tension during the lesson.

Another advantage of differentiation is that it develops the ability to work independently in students and allows you to allocate additional time to students who need more attention. Observations show that students prefer to work "one-on-one" with the teacher, ask their own questions, and receive explanations. It should be noted that the composition of the group can and must change. It is different in different lessons, so differentiation can be carried out according to different criteria [8]. The age factor may also have a considerable impact on comprehension [6].

Methods for determining differentiation:

The teacher determines whether differential training is needed in a lesson in accordance with the type, purpose and content of the lesson. A differential approach is more often used during application and repetition. Differentiation can be implemented in the following ways:

1. By the level of creativity (non-creative tasks include: working on a sample, answering factual questions, solving an example, etc. Creative tasks involve non-standard results: writing an essay, drawing a picture based on imagination, participating in a role-playing game, etc.);
2. By the level of difficulty;
3. By volume (additional tasks may be offered in accordance with the topic);
4. By the level of independence (all children perform the same task, some independently, others under the help and supervision of the teacher);
5. By the nature of the learning activity;
6. By the nature of the assistance provided to students (all children start work at the same time, and students who need assistance are provided with support in this way: auxiliary cards; giving easy but similar tasks; notes on the board, etc.) [10]. Audio and video tasks are also important [7], [9].

Auxiliary cards can be selected the same for all children in the group or individually. A student can receive several cards. The level of assistance provided to a student should be reduced for each lesson. Different types of support can be used on the cards:

1. an example of completing the task, a solution method, a reasoning example;
2. information materials;
3. notes;
4. illustrations, short texts, schemes;
5. focusing on small details;
6. auxiliary questions;

7. a plan for solving the task.

Differentiation methods can be interconnected, and tasks can be offered by choice. Learning new material: - When teaching a new topic, it is necessary to take into account the differences in learning skills and mental abilities of students. It depends on what kind of instruction students need and how difficult tasks for independent work will be selected. It is not so important to take into account the differences in students' knowledge when teaching new material, compared to other parts of the lesson process. When presenting new material, it is important to focus on as many different analyzers as possible (vision, hearing, movement, etc.), as this has a positive effect on memorization and understanding.

Conclusion

Focusing on the final result determines the teacher's differential approach to the material being taught. More time should be allocated to the assimilation of new material by "weak" students, while "strong" students can immediately be given independent tasks [19].

Reinforcement of the material studied. Differentiation is also important at the application stage. Here, students need tasks of different levels and a different number. At this stage of the lesson, "strong" students have time to complete additional tasks that expand and deepen their knowledge and skills. At the application stage, learning should be organized in such a way that each child, within his or her capabilities, can feel the success of learning each lesson and use the acquired skills in practice.

Control and assessment are aimed both at identifying the knowledge and skills acquired by students and, if necessary, at appropriate and timely correction of the process of forming this knowledge [14]. Control and assessment of student activity is carried out only in dynamics, that is, in comparison with previously acquired knowledge, and in no case does it involve comparing children with each other [15]. The main function of control and assessment is to monitor the progress of learning activities and identify errors in a timely manner [11].

It is important to minimize the stress that children experience during assessment. The atmosphere in the classroom should be calm and positive. Errors that occur during independent work are marked for completion and elimination. Thus, differential learning, referring to the interests and abilities of each student, creates conditions for deepening and expanding his knowledge and skills, eliminating his backwardness.

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